

CO2-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R10.1 Meeting minutes from Project meetings, General Assembly and End-User group meetings

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report documents the management of the Project and its key administrative activities, which include, inter alia, the work of the the Project's three governing bodies – the General Assembly, Management Board and End-User Group.

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body of the Project. All Partners involved in the Project had one representative in the General Assembly, their respective voting powers (number of votes) was corresponding to the scope of the Partner's involvement in the Project (in person-months of work). The General Assembly met four times (one meeting per year), the meetings took place as part of Project meetings.

The Management Board (steering committee) composed of the Project coordinator and the leaders of Work Packages, or representatives of the different institutions, although they did not lead any WP, supported the Project coordinator in operative project management. Management board closely collaborated throughout project duration. Management Board meetings were held on a monthly basis in the form of teleconferences or, where possible, in person during regular Project meetings. Minutes of the Management Board were entered into the ISTA system as part of the annual Interim reports.

Representatives of the main project target groups – industrial companies interested in the CCS technology, policy makers and regulators formed the End-User Group that served as the Project's main advisory body. The aim of the End-User Group meeting during the project was to present the results of the project to this group and to get valuable feedback from stakeholders on the progress and the future practical applicability of its results.

According to the Detailed Description of Work Packages (Annex to the Partnership Agreement), seven project meetings were planned in the domiciles of the partners but only four were organized face-to-face (Bergen, Brno, Hodonín, Ostrava) due to COVID pandemic situation – the first and second meetings were only held online. The project meetings played a crucial role in ensuring a smooth and successful Project completion.

2 MINUTES FROM PROJECT MEETINGS

CO2-SPICER – online Kick-off meeting

23 November 2020, 13:00 – 16:00

Participants:

CGS: Vit Hladík, Vladimír Kolejka, Eva Hudečková, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Patrik Fiferna, Aleš Havlín, Oldřich Krejčí, Jiří Rez, Róbert Prochác, Klára Froňková, Radek Svítal, Václav Pospíšil, Martin Paleček

MND: Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Vladimír Opletal, Lenka Klímová, Jana Hamršmídová

NORCE: Anders Nerموen, Eric Ford, Anton Shchipanov, Jan Tveranger, Ingebret Fjelde, Hans Petter Lohne

VSF: Martin Klempa, Martin Kašing, Monika Ličbinská, Naďa Rapartová, Krzysztof Labus, Jindřich Šancer, Michal Matloch Porzer, Matěj Křístek

GFU: Petr Kolář

Notes and actions:

1/ Welcome and introduction of participants

2/ Project presentation by project coordinator (slides available at Google Drive)

- Objectives: 3D storage complex, dynamic model, geochemistry and geomechanics, risks, future site development, Czech-Norwegian cooperation
- Results: 12 main, 41 others
- Communication plan – update must be finished until end of November 2020
- Overall context of CCS – V. Hladík informed about the new report Pathways to decarbonize the Czech Republic

<https://www.mckinsey.com/cz/our-work/pathways-to-decarbonize-the-czech-republic#>

3/ Presentation of the Zar-3 site

MND presented overview about geology, production history etc. of the Zar-3 field

4/ Introduction of Work Packages by WP leaders

All WP presentations are stored on Google Drive – temporary repository

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1mU3LJH3ZKnXv6p0hOTZHnWNzHOS41K>

Important: check the list and photos of core samples as announced by e-mail from V. Opletal see: <https://share.mnd.cz:5001/sharing/rmjg8W9DR>

5/ Work Communication and dissemination activities

- WP9 leader will circulate Communication Plan for updating and asks for quick response
Launch event is planned in December 2020; date will be confirmed till the end of November

Selected project logo will be stored on Google Drive, all published documents must be presented with unified graphics including logos: project, Norway grants, TA ČR, KAPPA Programme (not available yet)

- Project coordinator presentation about rules for presentations and publications: 2 guide documents – Communication and Design Manual EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021, Publicity Rules (see Google Drive / Kick-off meeting)

Note: Bilateral Fund for additional Czech-Norwegian activities, incl. presentation of joint results at conferences (if any?) is available; separate application needed.

6/ Administration and reporting

See Google Drive / Kick-off meeting

Notes: CO2-SPICER budget is more flexible than previous project REPP-CO2 – transfers between cost items in the same category (e.g. personnel costs of different staff members at different positions in the project) need not be reported, shifts between years and cost categories are possible to some extent.

P.Kolář asked for some project presentation (logos, mottos etc.) for his management – P.Fiferna promised a project leaflet and other project-introducing documents for all participants to be available in December 2020.

Notes taken by Eva and Vladimír, revised by Vít

CO2-SPICER – 2nd Project meeting

online, 30 November 2021, 9:30 – 15:50

Participants:

CGS: Vit Hladík, Vladimír Kolejka, Eva Hudečková, Patrik Fiferna, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Lukáš Jurenka, Daniela Ocásková, Petr Pařízek, Jiří Rez, Róbert Prochác

MND: Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Vladimír Opletal, Lenka Klímová, Štěpán Kaňa

NORCE: Anders Nermoen, Anton Shchipanov, Eric Ford, Ingebret Fjelde, Alexey Khruenko, Jan Tveranger, Hans Petter Lohne

VSB: Martin Klempa, Michal Matloch Porzer

GFU: Petr Kolář

Apologies:

NORCE: Roman Berenbyum

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction

- Project coordinator launched the meeting and described rules for online interaction.
- Main Partner representatives briefly introduced present team members from their institutions.
- Project coordinator summarized the general status of the project.

WP presentations

- WP leaders presented the status of their WPs, including progress and results achieved so far, plans for the upcoming period and issues encountered.
- All presentations will be uploaded to the project repository, folder NTS10_663600_SPICER/Project meetings and events/2nd_Project_meeting_2021-11-30
- Since the presentations contain all the important information, the minutes below focus only on issues that were discussed and resulting actions.

WP1 Data gathering and consolidation – Vladimir Kolejka

- Vladimir K. stressed the necessity to regularly (and without delay) update the Master table of samples with information on planned and executed tests and experiments in WPs 4 and 5, and with the changes that occur in the plan of utilisation of individual samples.
- He also asked all to keep the right abbreviations of wells in all documents and reports, as agreed in the beginning of the project (e.g. ZA3, UH11).
- Vit reminded all of the obligation to store all project data in the geodatabase. This includes both input data and any data produced by the project (by field measurements, lab tests and experiments, etc.).

WP2 3D geological model of the storage complex – Vladimir Opletal

- Vladimir O. mentioned some issues related to the construction of 3D reservoir model prepared by MND (e.g. porosity) that will be discussed at the modelling workshop on December 1.

- Vit reminded the larger 3D model of the storage complex, including the overburden, that is being prepared by CGS; synergies between the two workflows to be discussed at the modelling workshop.

WP3 Dynamic modelling and simulations – Milan Pagáč

- This WP is actually at the beginning – static 3D model is expected in spring 2022; issues will be discussed at the modelling workshop on December 1.
- Milan informed about the preparation for the step-rate test that had to be postponed to 2022. The pre-test last week was unsuccessful due to the low performance of the pump; another pre-test to be discussed to precede the full test next year.

WP4 Geomechanical characteristics – Anders Nerموen

- Discussion about suitable caprock core samples for geomechanical experiments (especially from Paleogene) was held; this issue will be discussed at the WP4-WP5 workshop on December 1 afternoon.
- Anders announced that he will start a paternity leave and plans to reduce his work engagement, incl. CO2-SPICER. During this time, Michal Matloch Porzer (VSB) will support him in WP4 leadership, incl. participation in the Management Board meetings.
- **Action Eva:** send Webex invitation to Michal Matloch Porzer for next MB meetings on December 16 – **deadline asap.**

WP5 Geochemistry of rocks and fluids – Juraj Franců

- The issue of suitable samples of reservoir water for chemical analysis and microbiology study was discussed; additional samples will be taken. This was followed by a discussion on the nature of oil samples and sampling methodology.
- **Action Juraj:** send Alexey information on crude oil analyses – **deadline asap.**

WP6 Risk analysis – Eric Ford

- Explanation of some unclear abbreviations in well log (sonic) reports is pending.
- Latest pieces of information about legacy wells (casing, penetration, cement plugs etc.) are still to be received.
- **Action MND:** help with these issues

WP7 Monitoring – Petr Jirman, with contributions by Vladimir Kolejka (report R7.4), Petr Kolář (Task 7.3 Seismic monitoring) and Anton Shchipanov (Task 7.5 Reservoir containment monitoring)

- Feasibility study (sub-contract) on applicability of seismic methods in T7.1 has been postponed to 2022.
- Consequences of WP3 step-rate test postponement for WP7 (seismic monitoring) were discussed; Petr K. to check if a re-installation of the temporary additional seismic network in 2022 is possible – it will depend on the availability of the monitoring stations.

WP8 Scenarios of future site development – Anton Shchipanov on behalf of Roman Berenblyum with contributions by Anders Nerموen and Alexey Khrulenko

- This WP is at the beginning; no significant issues were reported.

WP9 Communication and dissemination – Patrik Fiferna, with contribution by Vit Hladik on conference presentations and publications and liaison with other EEA/Norway Grants projects.

- Patrik alerted to the delayed contributions by some WP leaders to the 1st newsletter.
- **Action WP leaders (WP1+5+8):** prepare examples of current results for the 1st issue of the Project newsletter – short text with photos or pictures; VSB to provide pictures illustrating WP4 – **deadline December 3**
- Vit highlighted the plan to prepare a paper for the GHGT-16 conference (abstract submission deadline 14 January); contributions by WP leaders will be needed.

WP10 Project management and reporting – Eva Hudečková

- Eva informed about the TACR webinar on December 1 that will provide instructions for preparation of the 1st annual report. Representatives of all Czech partners were invited.
- **Action Eva, Vladimír, Vít:** inform all partners about conditions and instructions for the 1st annual reporting resulting from the TACR webinar on December 1 – **deadline asap.**
- Vit highlighted the fact that the 1st half of next year will be busy with many project results to be achieved (see presentation) and asked responsible colleagues to get ready for this in advance.

Discussion, question & answers

- Project coordinator expressed his general satisfaction with project progress so far and expressed his thanks to WP leaders, project administrator and the project team for their efforts in the 1st project year.

Notes taken by Eva and Vladimír, revised by Vít

CO2-SPICER – 3rd Project meeting

Bergen, 24 May 2022, 9:30 – 15:50

Participants:

CGS: Vít Hladík, Eva Hudečková, Patrik Fiferna, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Jiří Rez, Róbert Prochác

MND: Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Vladimír Opletal

NORCE: Roman Berenblyum, Anton Shchipanov, Eric Ford, Jan Tveranger, Walter Wheeler

VSB: Martin Klempa, Michal Matloch Porzer

GFU: Petr Kolář, Zuzana Jechumtálová

Online:

NORCE: Ingebret Fjelde

Apologies:

CGS: Vladimír Kolejka

NORCE: Anders Nerموen

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction

- Project coordinator launched the meeting and described rules for interaction.
- Main Partner representatives briefly introduced present team members from their institutions.
- Project coordinator summarized the general status of the project.

WP presentations

- WP leaders presented the status of their WPs, including progress and results achieved so far, plans for the upcoming period and issues encountered.
- All presentations will be uploaded to the project repository, folder NTS10_663600_SPICER/Project meetings and events/3rd_Project_meeting_2022-05-24
- Since the presentations contain all the important information, the minutes below focus only on issues that were discussed in more detail and resulting actions.

WP1 Data gathering and consolidation – Róbert Prochác & Petr Jirman on behalf of Vladimír K.

- The Master table of core samples must be regularly updated, including results of experiments (WP4 and WP5).
- The availability of suitable cores from caprock for geomechanical experiments (triaxial or Brazilian test) was discussed.
- In some cases, the same data is stored in duplicate in different folders of project repository; the authors are asked to check the stored data and delete outdated versions.
- All members were asked to keep the correct well abbreviations in all documents and reports, as agreed at the beginning of the project (e.g. ZA3, UH11); similarly the site name Zar-3 must be spelled correctly in all reports!
- Vít reminded the geodatabase subdivision into folders and their purpose

WP2 3D geological model of the storage complex – Vladimir Opletal

- Vladimir O. presented the model directly from the Petrel SW and explained the main features.
- The main differences in the MND and CGS interpretation of the Vranovice formation at the Zar-3 structure were discussed, including:
 - o different interpretation of the reservoir in the area of ZA12 well resulting in a difference in gross rock volume of the Zar-3 field, especially in the oil zone volume
 - o different approach to interpretation of the reservoir rock – while in the CGS geological model the oil-saturated zone is limited to Vranovice carbonates as a sole reservoir rock, the oil zone in the MND model contains combined Vranovice carbonate and Nikolčice clastic reservoir
- The main differences will be further discussed at the WP2-WP3-WP8 modelling workshop on Wednesday.
- The differences in both models show the interpretation precision of both teams and reflect the complexity of the geological settings, as well as the uncertainty inherent to input data (especially 3D seismic) in areas without presence of wells.
- Discussion was also held on the development of the reservoir structure shape and facies – a reef-like structure versus an erosional relict as a result of the deposition in the whole area and subsequent erosion to present form

WP3 Dynamic modelling and simulations – Milan Pagáč

- 3 geological models with different grid cell size have already been created and converted to dynamic models. Original grid size 50x50x10 m seemed to be too coarse for such small reservoir as Zar-3 field is. Therefore, model containing smaller grid blocks 25x25x10m was created. Finally, on the request of geologists, model with 10x10x5 m blocks was used in dynamic modelling. This relatively fine-grid model contains a high number of grid blocks causing much longer computational time. Comprehensive discussion about reducing the computational time took place during the modelling workshop.
- Preliminary results from history matching using 25x25x10m grid indicate that only limited aquifer volume may be connected with Zar-3 reservoir, which is obvious from observed bottom-hole pressure decline in the ZA3 observation well.
- Well test analysis of pressure transient data available from ZA4 well carried out by NORCE indicates permeability of 600 mD, skin factor of 12, which is in a perfect agreement with whole diameter core measurement carried out in OMV in 2002.
- Step-rate test (SRT): unsuccessful attempt was carried out at the end of 2021. SRT is planned for early June 2022.
- Modelling workshop: Apart from other issues, the following ones were discussed:
 - o How to use Fracture model created in CGS?
 - o What compressibility value to use in dynamic model?
 - o How to speed up simulation runs?

WP4 Geomechanical characteristics – Michal Matloch Porzer & Anton Shchipanov

- Available well cores from MND and each rock sample used by VSB are listed in Master table; sufficient number of samples will be discussed at tomorrow's workshop
- Original plan was to do all mechanical experiments and hand-over the raw geomechanical parameter data by 03/2022; this could not be kept – new caprock samples became available only in spring 2022 and experiments are planned for

summer. Nevertheless, the result R4.2 is ready in first version and will be updated after all experiments are finished.

- First dynamic response data after CO₂ exposure – data example presented of measurements on samples after 4 months exposure to oil-brine-CO₂ mixture

WP5 Geochemistry of rocks and fluids – Juraj Franců

- The current status of mineralogical and geochemical analyses includes:
 - o reservoir and caprock thin section petrography summarized in an upgraded atlas with photomicrographs in translucent, reflected and fluorescent light, sedimentological descriptions and interpreted depositional environment;
 - o special attention was given to optical porosity based on image analysis of macrophotos and photomicrographs;
 - o bulk rock chemistry using elemental analysis and x-ray fluorescence (mineral an organic carbon, sulphur, Na, Ca, Mg, ...)
 - o mineralogical composition of reservoir rocks and caprocks based on x-ray diffraction;
 - o chemical composition of the formation waters sampled from the wells; oil geochemistry using whole oil chromatography and biomarkers showing thermal maturity, source rocks and biodegradation;
 - o microbiological investigations of methanogenesis potential at Zar-3;
 - o experiments on CO₂ – water – rock interaction prepared and performed by VŠB
- The updated databases are stored in the project repository in WP5 folder. The mentioned topics were discussed during the WP2 modelling, WP6-WP5-WP2 risk and WP4-WP3-WP5 workshops on input from geomechanics and geochemistry to T3.3-5.
- First attempts were made to model numerically predicted changes in reservoir and caprock matrices and mineral neoformations. In the next phase, the models will be improved using the experimental lab data (pre- and post-reaction analyses).
- **Action Juraj:** send information on accessible results to everybody involved in WP5, organize WP video-meeting with MND, VSB and NORCE partners; **deadline early September**

WP6 Risk analysis – Eric Ford

- Wells overview – what wells would come into contact with CO₂?
- Preliminary risking - Risk evaluation only based on length of barrier against assumed annulus leak path/against assumed plug leak path
- Fault reactivation possibility to be studied
- Results from WP5 were mentioned and how they may be used together with geomechanical data for the evaluation of the reservoir containment, seal efficiency and probability of fluid escape to the overlying formations.

WP7 Monitoring – Petr Jirman, with contributions by Petr Kolář (Task 7.3 Seismic monitoring) and Anton Shchipanov (Task 7.5 Reservoir containment monitoring)

- The tender for sub-contract on Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods in T7.1 is being prepared
- Injection step-rate test (second attempt) including the induced seismicity monitoring is scheduled for the beginning of next month; temporary seismic stations are operating
- Shallow hydrogeological model of groundwater flow (using MODFLOW SW) will be created by VSB in second half of 2022

- Plans for dipole electromagnetic profiling data interpretation and analysis of possible leakage pathways (to be received from WP6) were discussed
- Task 7.3: overview of up to now performed seismic monitoring and data processing (incl. precise locations); confirmed earlier agreed one year prolongation of seismic monitoring and data processing

WP8 Scenarios of future site development – Roman Berenblyum

- Several possible scenarios based on different possible CO₂ sources and resulting different injection rates were presented and discussed

WP9 Communication and dissemination – Patrik Fiferna

- In addition to WP status overview, Patrik presented overview of planned peer-reviewed publications; many of them belong to binding (“main”) project results. Related manuscripts must be finalised and submitted well in advance to keep the delivery deadlines.
- Patrik also reminded the Publication rules according to the Partnership Agreement

WP10 Project management and reporting – Eva Hudečková

- Eva provided information about liaison with TACR so far (online consultation 06/2021, monitoring visit “on site” 09/2021 and consultation per rollam 01/2022), submission of the 1st annual report in January 2022 and rapporteur’s standpoint on the good quality and completeness of the report.
- She also emphasized the lower budget consumption in 2021 (ca 73 % of the plan) and rapporteur’s recommendation to pay special attention to matching the project timeline
- Brief overview of project results achieved so far, postponed and remaining results in 2022 was provided (see presentation)

Discussion, question & answers

- Project coordinator expressed his general satisfaction with project progress so far.
- Project coordinator informed about the “on-site” audit by TACR that was announced by TACR just one day before the meeting day and that will focus on project progress and achievements until 03/2022. Technical part of the audit will examine project results that were due within the period in question, while the administrative and financial part will be mainly devoted to check of costs incurred by project partners CGS and MND. Suggested timing of the audit is 20-21 June 2022.

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková, contributions provided by Milan Pagáč, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Róbert Prochác, Patrik Fiferna, Petr Kolář, Michal Matloch Porzer, revised by Vít Hladík

CO2-SPICER – 4th Project meeting

Brno, 7 December 2022, 9:00 – 16:20

Participants:

CGS: Vít Hladík, Vladimír Kolečka, Eva Hudečková, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Daniela Ocásková, Petr Pařízek

MND: Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Vladimír Opletal

NORCE: Roman Berenblyum, Anders Nermoen

VSU: Martin Klempa, Michal Matloch Porzer

GFU: Petr Kolář, Zuzana Jechumtálová

Online:

NORCE: Anton Shchipanov, Eric Ford, Jan Tveranger, Walter Wheeler, Hans Petter Lohne

Apologies:

CGS: Patrik Fiferna

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction

- Project coordinator launched the meeting and described rules for interaction
- Tour de table - brief introduction of meeting participants
- Project coordinator summarized the general status of the project (see presentation)

WP presentations

- WP leaders presented the status of their WPs, including progress and results achieved so far, plans for the upcoming period and issues encountered.
- All presentations will be uploaded to the project repository, folder NTS10_663600_SPICER/Project meetings and events/4th_Project_meeting_2022-12-07
- Since the presentations contain all the important information, the minutes below focus only on issues that were discussed in more detail and resulting actions.

WP1 Data gathering and consolidation – Vladimír Kolečka

- The Master table of core samples must be regularly updated, including results of experiments (WP4 and WP5).
- English version of result R1.2 was finalised.
- The availability of additional suitable cores from caprock for geomechanical experiments (triaxial or Brazilian test) is very limited (MND to check), task T1.2 is nearly finishing.
- Open data access must be provided to all data created in the project except those defined confidential; this will be done using Zenodo repository as planned. For results “J-type” (peer-reviewed articles), open access must be provided as well; where needed the authors must plan open access payment (small budget for this is reserved in CGS budget but this will be not enough for all publications).

WP2 3D geological model of the storage complex – Vladimír Opletal

- Result V1 and its Appendix contain set of structural geological maps both in regional and reservoir scale
- The main issues (petrophysical parameters distribution etc.) will be further discussed at the WP2-WP3-WP8 modelling workshop on Thursday.

WP3 Dynamic modelling and simulations – Milan Pagáč

- Task T3.2 – postponed step-rate-test represents the main issue for this task and influences several WPs; the potential term for this test is summer 2023
- Task T3.3 – Minimum Miscibility Pressure (MMP) of 165 bars was estimated based on correlations in the literature and the PVT model. MMP is one of the key parameters affecting the performance of the EOR in compositional reservoir modelling and, of course, the EOR process itself.
- Task T3.4 – permeability distribution does not accurately match PTA analysis (yet), MND with NORCE are working on permeability distribution improvement and new history match will be required.
- Task T3.5 – the 1st scenario of injection simulation was created
- Plans for 2023: new permeability distribution matching PTA results; new History match; scenarios of CO₂ injection simulation; upscaling of geochemical, geomechanical and compositional effects; **carrying out and analysing the Step-rate-test (hopefully not too late for incorporating its results into simulation)**

WP4 Geomechanical characteristics – Anders Nerموen

- Anders restarted his position of WP leader on August 15, 2022, after paternity leave
- Update of the result draft R4.2 (03/2022) is ongoing, final version is expected before Christmas; result R4.3 will be finalized before end of 2022
- Main issues: delays in mechanical experiments; no clear trend in ultrasonic stiffness changes – inconclusive data so far - disclaimer when applying these results, the stiffness and strengths of the weaker parts of the reservoir were not tested; milestone M4.1 (handover of WP4 work to WP3) is delayed
- Main result V11 – uncertainty in the topic of peer-reviewed article – potential change in topic must be consulted with TACR in advance

WP5 Geochemistry of rocks and fluids – Juraj Franců

- Next set of analyses of fluids and rocks (inorganic geochemistry; organic geochemistry of light hydrocarbons, biomarkers in rocks & oils and isotopes) has been performed.
- Next experiments: complete CO₂-water-cap rock experiments until spring 2023, reactive geochemical modelling (equilibrium models, kinetic models, salt precipitation)
- Time issue: geochemical results have to be included into 3D modelling & simulation scenarios but are not yet ready; e.g. results of XRD are currently only in graphic form; reactive modelling still to be started. **Intensive cooperation of all actors – CGS, VSB, NORCE – is needed to provide the necessary outcomes.**

WP6 Risk analysis – Eric Ford

- Map of caprock thickness in grid form – caprock thickness is currently only in form of isoline maps, this issue will be discussed at special online risk workshop on Tuesday 13 December
- Fault stability/reactivation – structural geological map with faults of the wider area is needed, will be prepared by CGS (task T6.1.3)

- Plans for Q1, Q2/2023: Finalizing Task 6.1 (incl. sensitivity analysis, formation fluids displacement, caprock integrity assessment, seal chemical reactivity assessment /input from WP5/, seal entry pressure – probably no measured data); will be followed by completing exposure and effect assessments

WP7 Monitoring – Petr Jirman, with contributions by Petr Kolář (Task 7.3 Seismic monitoring) and Anton Shchipanov (Task 7.5 Reservoir containment monitoring)

- The tender for sub-contract on Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods in T7.1 is closed –one bid submitted, currently under evaluation
- Injection step-rate test was postponed, use of temporary seismic stations for related seismicity monitoring is unclear
- Shallow hydrogeological model of groundwater flow (using MODFLOW SW) was postponed and will be created by VSB in 2023
- Dipole electromagnetic profiling data gathered by VSB – further analysis of possible leakage pathways is ongoing

WP8 Scenarios of future site development – Roman Berenblyum

- Well recompletion: Does the potential injection well need to be recompleted?
- CO2 transport scenarios – 25t truck vs. 14/8 t trucks, cost estimation
- Selection of the most suitable CO2 source, capture cost estimation
- Pilot scenario development (20-90 kt CO2 in total)
- Transition to long term scenario? Including temporary EOR?
- Plans for Q1/2023: NORCE - First evaluation of the scenarios (economy, abated emission), input by CGS / MND - Preparation for regional scenario (selected emitters and storage sites for regional scenario)

WP9 Communication and dissemination – Vít Hladík on behalf of Patrik Fiferna

- New logo, graphic style and templates, website - updated graphics
- Updated Communication Plan (R9.5) finalised
- Issues: delayed set-up of the End-User Club, additional funding from Bilateral Fund currently unavailable, not all partners are active in the WP

WP10 Project management and reporting – Eva Hudečková

- Information on TACR audit performed in summer 2022: positive outcome of both financial (June 20) and technical (July 21) parts; subsequent KAPPA team online consultation (November 2) concerning methodology of using company cars and N_{map} results format
- Interim reporting 2022 – brief reminder of the last year's procedure and instructions on the required documents.
Deadline for Interim report submission is 30 January 2023 – **deadline for all inputs is 16 January 2023**
- Brief overview of results to be delivered in 2022

Discussion, question & answers

- Project coordinator expressed his general satisfaction with project progress so far.
- Main issues and immediate actions:
 - o Finalise all 2022 results before Christmas
 - o Prepare a good-quality 2022 Interim Report and submit it on time

- All WP leaders to prepare a good updated work plan for the rest of the project to achieve objectives and deliver results on time
- Try to speed up the step-rate-test in WP3
- Improve communication among partners!

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková and Vladimír Kolejka, revised by Vít Hladik

CO2-SPICER – 5th Project meeting

Hodonín, 13 June 2023, 12:15 – 17:00

Participants:

CGS: Vladimír Kolejka, Eva Hudečková, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman

MND: Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Štěpán Káňa

NORCE: Roman Berenblyum, Alexey Khrulenko

VSB: Martin Klempa, Michal Matloch Porzer, Monika Ličbinská

GFU: Petr Kolář

Online:

NORCE: Anton Shchipanov, Anders Nerموen, Ingebret Fjelde

Apologies:

CGS: Patrik Fiferna

MND: Vladimír Opletal, Lenka Klímová

NORCE: Eric Ford

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction

- Mr. Sasín opened the meeting as representative of MND as a host
- Project coordinator, Juraj Franců, summarized the general status of the project (see the presentation)

WP presentations

- WP leaders presented the status of their WPs, including progress and results achieved so far, plans for the upcoming period and issues encountered.
- All presentations will be uploaded to the project repository, folder NTS10_663600_SPICER/Project meetings and events/5th_Project_meeting_2023-06-13
- Since the presentations contain all the important information, the minutes below focus only on issues that were discussed more in detail and resulting actions.

WP1 Data gathering and consolidation – Vladimír Kolejka

- Tasks T1.1 and T1.2 were finished
- Task T1.3 - data transfer from CO2-SPICER data repository into open access repository (Zenodo) is under preparation
- Discussion on open data access – which data will be open to public? Only secondary data (e.g. results of experiments) will be accessible, no input data.
- Project structure (WP1-WP7) corresponds to valid legislation – CCS EU Directive and Czech Act no. 85/2012

WP2 3D geological model of the storage complex – Vladimír Opletal apologised + **WP3**

Dynamic modelling and simulations – Milan Pagáč

- 3D static model was finalised with changes required by dynamic modelling

- Issues of dynamic modelling: horizontal or follow-base grid? Distribution of petrophysical parameters – channel of high permeability does not correspond to history match (see presentation)
- Simulation of CO₂ injection for feasibility study (sub-contract) is ongoing

WP4 Geomechanical characteristics – Anders Nerموen online

- Geomechanical tests and conditions of safe CO₂ injection :
 - o Pore pressure & temperature range
 - o Impacts of rock-fluid interactions (?)
- Geomechanical tests – UCS, triaxial, sound velocity measurement and tensile strength were finalized
- Rock strengths at failure were measured, Earth stress was estimated in three ways
- Effect of pressure and reservoir temperature ranges was evaluated for injection of cold CO₂
- Discussion: is pressure about 4 MPa (after gas production) safe?
- Milan asks Anders for a contribution to the main result V12 (multiple hydrostatic cycle)

WP5 Geochemistry of rocks and fluids – Juraj Franců, Monika Ličbinská

- 121 cuttings samples have been analysed for elemental and geochemical composition
- Existing pre-experiment XRD mineralogical analyses will be complemented by post-experiment ones (in process)
- Biomarkers in rock extracts and oils are being evaluated to provide fluid variability in reservoir and cap rocks
- Monika: geological and permeability input data for modelling SW Toughreact have been provided by MND colleagues (thank you); mineral dissolution and neoformations are simulated in the reservoir, closer link to the dynamic model (WP3) is desirable

WP6 Risk analysis – Roman Berenblyum on behalf of Eric Ford

- Simulations of gas concentration levels vs various threshold levels as a function of distance from release points were done. Purpose is to visualize exposure risk per group in the form of risk maps
- Attention will be focussed at exposure effect on different groups specific to site: humans, animals – species, vegetation, streams, ground water and infrastructure

WP7 Monitoring – Petr Jirman, with contributions by Petr Kolář (Task 7.3 Seismicity monitoring) and Anton Shchipanov (Task 7.5 Reservoir containment monitoring)

- Roman Pevzner and Boris Gurevich have been sub-contracted and will prepare a Feasibility study on Applicability of seismic monitoring methods in the task T7.1
- T7.2. Atmogeoechemical monitoring - 7th campaign finished
- T7.3 Seismicity monitoring - data processing is ongoing
- T7.4 Shallow groundwater monitoring - the preliminary results indicate no anomalies; issue - task leader Aleš Havlín left CGS in April 2023
- Shallow hydrogeological model of groundwater flow (using MODFLOW SW) is ongoing (VSB Nad'a Rapantová)
- T7.5 Reservoir containment monitoring - injection step-rate test was postponed (early October 2023), use of stations for related seismicity monitoring during the Step-rate-test depends on extra funding (negotiations with MND is desirable)
- T7.6. Site monitoring plan – starts in July 2023 summarizing experience from all WP7 tasks

WP8 Scenarios of future site development – Roman Berenblyum

- Discussion on potential CO₂ injection well – well ZA7 is most suitable injector, ZA3 can be used as monitoring well
- CO₂ transport scenarios – 25t truck vs. 14/8 t trucks, cost estimation
- Selection of the most suitable CO₂ source, capture cost estimation (up to 500 EUR per tonne)
- Pilot scenario development – 70 kt CO₂ in total during 2 years injection
- Estimated cost: CAPEX – 107 thousand EUR, OPEX – 22 mil EUR, scenario for 20 bar and 7 °C
- Direct capture – very expensive, cost and emission during transport can be less suitable than direct capture
- Update of infrastructure (platform ZA3 + ZA7) and update of CO₂ emission list is needed

WP9 Communication and dissemination – Juraj Franců on behalf of Patrik Fiferna

- 3 poster presentations are accepted for the TCCS-12 Meeting in Trondheim in June 2023
- Czech-Norwegian CCS workshop in Norway will take place in Scandic Lerkendal hotel in Trondheim on Monday, June 19, 2023
- 2 presentations are accepted for IMOG conference in Montpellier in September 2023
- 6th Project meeting in Ostrava – 3rd-4th week in November 2023 will be organized by VSB
- Final Project conference will take place in Prague in April 2024 – discussion on suitable place (GFU offered venue), possibility of joint conference with parallel KAPPA project Metamorph?

WP10 Project management and reporting – Eva Hudečková

- Detailed discussion of progress on planned main results in 2023-2024
Issues:
 - V2 (type N_{map}) – joint result WP3 + WP8 – output from WP3 was postponed, final history match will be in September 2023
 - V3 (type N_{map}) – WP1 maps are ready on the repository, input from WP6, WP7, WP8 is in preparation phase – Vladimír Kolejka is coordinator of the V3 joint result.
 - V4 (type O) – WP6 no issue expected
 - V5 (type O) – WP7 possible issue – result of sub-contracted feasibility study of seismic monitoring
 - V6 (type O) – WP8 no issue expected
 - V7 (type O) – WP9 – discussion with TAČR is needed (V7 vs R10.3, interim report for period 01-04/2024?)
 - V8 (type O) – WP9 – Summarizing paper on the project achievements is planned for June 2024 (J. Francu with the team)
 - V9 (type J) – WP5 oral presentation at IMOG Sep 2023, publication Feb 2024
 - V10 (type J) – WP6 (risk) no issue expected
 - V11 (type J) – WP4, according to Anders draft is ready
 - V12 (type J) – WP3, Milan asked Anders for a contribution to the result (multiple hydrostatic cycle)

Discussion, question & answers

- Juraj asked Roman about possible increased Ingebret involvement (capacity and funding of experiment on salt precipitation) in the project.

- Project coordinator expressed his big Thank You to the team members for the project progress so far.

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková and Vladimír Kolečka, revised by Juraj Franců

CO2-SPICER – 6th Project meeting

Ostrava, 21 November 2023, 10:00 – 17:00

Participants:

CGS: Vladimír Kolečka, Eva Hudečková, Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Patrik Fiferna

MND: Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Vladimír Opletal

VSB: Martin Klempa, Michal Matloch Porzer

GFU: Petr Kolář

Online:

NORCE: Roman Berenblyum, Eric Ford, Anton Shchipanov, Anders Nerموen

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction

- Martin Klempa opened the meeting as representative of VSB as a host
- Project coordinator, Juraj Franců, summarized the general status of the project (see the presentation)

WP presentations

- WP leaders presented the status of their WPs, including progress and results achieved so far, plans for the upcoming period and issues encountered.
- All presentations will be uploaded to the project repository, folder NTS10_663600_SPICER/Project meetings and events/6th_Project_meeting_2023-11-21
- Since the presentations contain all the important information, the minutes below focus only on issues that were discussed more in detail and resulting actions.

WP1 Data gathering and consolidation – Vladimír Kolečka

- Progress in main result V3 (joint WP1, WP6, WP7 and WP8, N_{map} type, 12/2023); result structure corresponds to valid legislation – maps will be arranged according to Act no. 85/2012

WP2 3D geological model of the storage complex + WP3 Dynamic modelling and simulations – Milan Pagáč

- As agreed during the previous project meeting in Hodonín, new history match using dipping (follow base) grid was accomplished. But the history match has not been approved, some changes in property distribution in the dynamic model are required according to NORCE proposal
- Milan presented CO2-SPICER project at CO2GeoNet Open Forum in Venice in October 2023 and thanked to the other WP's leaders for providing slides as a basis for the presentation; presentation was uploaded to the project repository, folder NTS10_663600_SPICER/Project meetings and events/CO2GeoNet_Venice2023
- Milan asked Anders (WP4 geomechanics leader) for contribution to V12
- Deadline change of the main result V12 (peer-reviewed scientific article) will be discussed with TACR.

- The 3D dynamic modelling was presented and discussed more in detail on the workshop on 22 November 2023.

WP4 Geomechanical characteristics – Anders Nerموen

- Experimental part of WP4 was finalized
- Anders has prepared 3 papers – one of them has been recently submitted:
 - o “Evaluation of safe operating envelope for CO₂ injection under variability and uncertainty in rock mechanical parameters and Earth stresses”
 - o “Geomechanical data base of rock samples from the Žarošice hydrocarbon and storage complex (South Moravia, Czech Republic): Petrophysics, stiffness, strength, and effective stress estimates for stability evaluations during CO₂ injection” is being prepared for publishing in International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control (IJGGC)
 - o “Using innovative statistical tools for hypothesis testing. Methodological development”, this paper is in preparation.

WP5 Geochemistry of rocks and fluids – Juraj Franců

- 121 cuttings samples have been analysed for elemental and biomarker composition.
- Existing pre-experiment XRD mineralogical analyses have been complemented by post-experiment ones.
- Biomarkers in rock extracts and oils are being evaluated to provide fluid variability in reservoir and cap rocks.
- Monika Ličbinská presented model of mineral dissolution and neof ormations in the Zar-3 storage site.
- Caprock type 1,2,3 geochemical analysis provide basis for risk analysis dealt with in WP6.
- Result R5.2 (11/23) Geochemistry of fluids – oils, formation waters and gases.
- Result R5.3 (12/23)
- Result R5.4 (12/23)
- Result V9 “Peer-reviewed article presenting results of geochemical characterization of Zar-3 storage site” 4/2024; similar topic “Geochemistry of fluids and minerals in reservoir and caprocks” was presented at IMOG conference in Montpellier Sep 2023, paper manuscript for International Journal of Organic Geochemistry (or similar) is under preparation to be submitted in January 2024.

WP6 Risk analysis – Eric Ford

- Result V2 “Risk assessment report” is near completion; to be added – drinking water sources (map of drinking water pipelines); is there any re-abandoned well?
- **Result R6.4 “Data set and report with results of well integrity logging” (10/2023)** - will be finalized by MND (Hrdličková) and KaC = Logging and cementing (Šťastný) and revised by CGS. Chapter on caprocks will be provided by Juraj et al.

WP7 Monitoring – Petr Jirman, with contributions by Petr Kolář (Task 7.3 Seismicity monitoring)

- T7.1 – final version of “Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ Plume monitoring” was accepted by CGS last week and **Result 7.8 “Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ Plume monitoring” (12/2023)** will be revised by CGS
- T7.2 – all atmogeochemical monitoring campaigns were finished, data are under processing, work on result R7.3 and maps preparation for result V3 is ongoing. **Result**

7.3 “Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results” (11/2023) – draft is ready

- T7.3 – data from seismic monitoring are intensively processed, Petr K. presented preliminary results. Result R7.7 “Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring” 4/2024
- T7.4 – Naďa Rapantová and Juraj are new task leaders; Naďa will present preliminary results of ground water modelling during tomorrow’s workshop. **Result R7.5 “Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring” (11/2023) – draft is ready**
- T7.5 reservoir containment monitoring - **Result R7.6 “Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring” (3/2023)** - depends on step-rate-test; workover on ZA7 well was finalized last week, the possibility of step-rate-test in December 2023 is still open

WP8 Scenarios of future site development – Roman Berenblyum

- Result V2 “Set of 3D models and maps with result of dynamic modelling” (1/24) – some delay is expected
- Potential “post-Spicer” project – capture from local compressor facility storage max 10 tons per day; depends on MND decision

WP9 Communication and dissemination – Patrik Fiferina

- Brief overview of all activities in WP9
- Plans: Article in popular science journal (2023), Press releases (4/2024), final Project newsletter (4/2024) and Final project conference (4/2024)
- Final Project conference will take place in Prague in March/April 2024 – voting is being prepared

WP10 Project management and reporting – Eva Hudečková

- Brief information on preparation of the Interim report 2023 – all necessary documents were reminded
- Overview of results to be delivered in 2023 with stress on main results

Discussion, question & answers

- Juraj asked all participants to vote on the final conference date
- Next MB will be held on the irregular date on 13 December at the usual time 13:30

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková and Vladimír Kolečka, revised by Juraj Franců

3 MINUTES FROM GENERAL ASSEMBLY

CO2-SPICER – 1th General Assembly meeting

online, 30 November 2021, 16:00 – 16:30

Participants:

GA members:

CGS: Vít Hladík

MND: Milan Pagáč (representing GA member Tomáš Baldrián)

NORCE: Anton Shchipanov (representing GA member Roman Berenblyum)

VSB: Martin Klempa

GFU: Petr Kolář

Observers:

Eva Hudečková (project administrator)

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction by Vit Hladik

Legal status of the project – contracts and agreements

Vit Hladik provided an overview of contractual status of the project:

- Project Contract (Grant Agreement)
- Partnership Agreement
- Non-Disclosure Agreement (between MND and CGS, NORCE, VSB)

See presentation slides in attachment for details.

Progress of work, discussion of delays and possible issues

GA members agreed that progress of work presented at the Project meeting (preceding the GA) is satisfactory.

Vit Hladik presented the main items that have been delayed:

- WP3 – step-rate test; postponed to early 2022 due to unavailability of equipment at MND. The pre-test carried out last week was unsuccessful due to insufficient performance of the pump. The temporary additional seismic network installed now on the site by GFU will need to be removed, and it is uncertain if the equipment is available for the postponed test in 2022. GFU will check possibilities.
NORCE and MND agreed that, as a lesson learned, another pre-test will be carried out before the main test in 2022 and before the temporary seismic network is re-installed.
- WP6 – well integrity logging – postponed to 2022 because of its dependence on well work-over plans of MND (no opportunity to perform it in 2021).
- WP7 – seismic monitoring feasibility study – postponed to 2022, after the 3D geological model is available (approved by the Management Board); NORCE suggested help of Norwegian colleagues based on experience with carbonates; appreciated by CGS.

GA members agreed that the discussed delays are not critical for project progress.

GA members did not identify any additional issues related to project execution.

Communication among partners, possible issues

GA members discussed internal communication within the project framework. Slight issues were observed in communication between project partners in early stages of the project, which partly caused later involvement of NORCE researchers in some WPs. This has now been solved.

Occasional issues were noted in communication of project-wide items to team members outside the Management Board. The General Assembly therefore recommends:

- to the Management Board members to improve internal communication towards other team members both within their own institutions and within their Work Packages;
- to the Project administration team of CGS to keep the Project repository up-to-date so that it can serve as a good information source for all project team members.

Project budget, expected expenditures in Year 1

Vit Hladik informed that 2020-21 expenditures are expected to be below the plan, due to postponed sub-contracts (as discussed earlier) and reduced travel costs.

Anton Shchipanov informed that NORCE budget spending at the end of 2021 is estimated to be about 60 % of the plan (to be confirmed later).

The TACR KAPPA threshold of 70% annual budget spending of the whole consortium was discussed. It is recommendable to achieve it but even in case this is not reached, the consequences are not severe – TACR may reduce or delay the pre-financing for 2022 but the overall budget remains untouched.

Year 1 reporting – principal requirements

The interim report will consist of two main parts:

- Technical report – text report following the structure of the project and describing project progress. Administration team will prepare a template, WP leaders will be responsible for WP-related chapters.
- Tables and information to be filled in in the ISTA online system, including cost statements of all partners.

CGS and other Czech partners will take part in the TACR instructing webinar „How to prepare interim report for 2021“ (in Czech only) that will take place on December 1. Materials from the webinar will be distributed to project partners asap.

Decision whether the cost statements and other input in the ISTA system will be completed by CGS for the whole consortium, or by individual partners themselves will be made at the next Management Board meeting.

Eva Hudeckova alerted to the issue of compulsory recalculation of person-year capacities per each project team position according to the real situation (as reflected in the time sheets).

Any other business

None.

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková, revised by Vít Hladík

CO2-SPICER – 2nd General Assembly meeting

Hotel Continental Brno, 7 December 2022, 16:35 – 16:50

Participants:

GA members:

CGS: Vít Hladík

MND: Milan Pagáč (representing GA member Tomáš Baldrián)

NORCE: Roman Berenblyum

VSB: Martin Klempa

GFU: Petr Kolář

Observers:

Eva Hudečková (project administrator)

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction by Vit Hladik

Overall status of the project, results of audits

Vit Hladik provided an overview of actual status of the project:

- Project is running relatively well with some delays
- Results of TACR audit performed in summer 2022: positive outcome of both technical and financial parts. One minor finding - some CGS costs were found to be ineligible (fuel for company cars – 1306 CZK), this issue was discussed with TACR in online consultation – invoices are needed in any case, only Governmental decree on fuel prices is not enough – it limits the maximum price but it must be always supplemented by invoice or bill, the fuel price per litre must be compared and the lower value must be used for cost calculation.

Progress of work, discussion of delays and possible issues

GA members agreed that progress of work presented at the Project meeting (preceding the GA) is satisfactory.

Vit Hladik presented the main items that have been delayed:

- WP3 – step-rate test; postponed to summer 2023 due to long term of tubing delivery; this influences several WPs that will need to cope with new results in 2nd half of 2023.
- Delivery of WP2 and WP4 results – all results are expected to be delivered for the 2022 Interim report (i.e. by the end of the year).
- Explanation of work delays shall be reported in individual WP chapters of the Technical report (part of the 2022 Interim report) – e.g. WP4 Anders's paternity leave, WP3 step-rate-test, etc. Milestones to be reported as well. Vít will summarize main delays and explanations in chapter Obstacles of the Technical report.

GA members agreed that the discussed delays are not critical for achievement of project objectives and periodic reporting.

GA members did not identify any additional issues related to project execution.

Communication among partners, possible issues

Vit raised the issue of decreasing level (quality) of internal communication within the project framework. Issues were observed in communication between project participants (long reaction times or no reactions to requests / e-mails, Actions delayed or not performed without explanation, etc.). GA members were asked to emphasize the importance of responsible and active communication to colleagues in their organisations and ask them to improve communication quality – the issue is related to overall commitment to the project and achievement of its objectives.

Conclusion: The General Assembly asks the Management Board members to ensure improvement of internal project communication towards other team members both within their own institutions and within the Work Packages.

Project budget, expected expenditures in Year 2:

- CGS expects small overspending, mainly in personal costs
- VSB is in frame of the planned budget
- GFU follows the updated budget till the end of the project – budgeted for 2022 was decreased while budget for 2023 was increased due to prolongation of seismic monitoring
- MND budget must be updated, keep in mind last-year underspending (!)
- NORCE budget spending in NOK is expected to be in accordance with planned budget but the spending in CZK might be exceeded due to change of exchange rate between NOK and CZK; keep in mind last-year underspending (!)

Year 2 reporting – principal requirements

- **All input from partners must be delivered on time (January 16, 2023)!**

Any other business

None.

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková, revised by Vít Hladík

CO2-SPICER – 3rd General Assembly meeting

Hodonín venue MND, 14 June 2023, 10:10 – 10:20

Participants:

GA members:

- CGS: Juraj Franců
- MND: Milan Pagáč (on behalf of Tomáš Baldrián)
- NORCE: Roman Berenblyum
- VSB: Martin Klempa
- GFU: Petr Kolář

Observers:

- Eva Hudečková (project administrator)

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction by Juraj Franců

Project budget, expected expenditures in Year 3 and total project expenditure:

Juraj Franců provided an overview of actual spending on the project:

- VSB is in frame of the planned budget
- GFU follows the updated budget till the end of the project – budgeted for 2022 was decreased while budget for 2023 was increased due to prolongation of seismic monitoring; in case of further extension of the use of temporary seismic stations for related seismicity monitoring due to the postponed step-rate-test, the GFU would need more money (150-180 thousand) and the capacity of experts is not certain – money transfer between project partners to be communicated with TAČR
- NORCE assume full use of the money; CGS proposed a slight overrun due to the changing NOK-CZK exchange rate but according to internal rules, it must not exceed the planned amount
- MND – a special meeting with MND economist will be held after finishing GA, it seems that MND will not spent its budget as planned, expected saving about 0.6 million CZK
- Half-year reporting – budget expenditure for the period 01-06/2023 to be submitted with the corresponding timesheets for all partners and participants

TCCS conference in Trondheim on 19-21 June, 2023

- Czech-Norwegian CCS workshop in Norway will be organized in frame of TCCS-12 conference in Trondheim on Monday June 19, 2023 in Scandic Lerkendal hotel from 16:00 to 18:00
- The workshop will be attended by 3 representatives from CGS (Eva, Juraj, Petr J.), 2 from MND (Vladimír O., Jiří) and Roman, Eric, Anders and Ingebret will participate on behalf of the Norwegian partner

6th project meeting in Ostrava

This meeting will be organized by VSB, after a short discussion it was suggested the 3rd-4th week of November 2023, details to be worked out after the holidays at the regular Management board meeting in September.

Final conference in Prague in April 2024

GFU has offered to host the conference at their premises, but it depends on whether we host the conference ourselves on behalf of the CO2-SPICER project or join with the parallel KAPPA Metamorph project. It was agreed to contact the principal investigator of the second project and proceed with the planning according to his/her decision.

Open access to the project data

Subsequently, there was a discussion among GA members on:

- Which data will be open to public? Members decided to make only secondary data available to the public (e.g. results of experiments)!
- Where should the data be stored? Zenodo? It is necessary to contact researchers of other similar projects or to look on the Internet or discuss with TAČR agency.

Any other business

None.

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková, revised by Juraj Franců

CO2-SPICER – 4th General Assembly meeting

Praha Plaza Hotel, 19 March 2024, 16:20 – 16:40

Participants:

GA members:

- CGS: Juraj Franců
- MND: Milan Pagáč (on behalf of Tomáš Baldrián)
- NORCE: Roman Berenblyum
- VSF: Martin Klempa
- GFU: Petr Kolář

Observers:

- Eva Hudečková (project administrator)

Meeting minutes:

Welcome and introduction by Juraj Franců

Final conference in Prague

- General Assembly (GA) expressed satisfaction with today's Final conference

General Assembly took note of announced Deloitte Advisory review:

- Our project was selected on the basis of a contract between Deloitte Advisory and the Ministry of Finance to verify whether the project is implemented in accordance with the conditions and methodological documents set by the programme facilitator (TA CR); Wednesday 20 March, 2024 at 9:00

General Assembly approved establishment of End-User Group

- Members: Lime Producers Association CR, Gas Storage CZ, UNIGEO, Heidelberg Materials CZ (ČM cement)

Open access to the project data

- Special directory "CO2-SPICER TO1000112" on repository Zenodo was created and successfully tested for data uploading

Main results issue

- Main result V12 "Peer-reviewed article presenting results of reservoir simulation" is delayed; GA decided to ask TA CR for postponement of the submission deadline by 30 June, 2024. Application for this postponement must be submitted to TA CR before 15 April, 2024. GA authorised Juraj to negotiate this issue with Mr. Toman - TA CR responsible person for our project

Any other business

None.

Notes taken by Eva Hudečková, revised by Juraj Franců

4 MINUTES FROM END-USER GROUP MEETINGS

CO2-SPICER – End-User Group meeting

Praha Plaza Hotel, 19 March 2024, 12:00 – 12:30

Participants:

Invited Members:

Eva Hejralová – Climate Protection Policy Department, Ministry of the Environment CZ

Lukáš Peřka – Executive Director, Czech Lime Association (Svaz výrobců vápna ČR)

Petr Badžgoň – Health, Safety and Environmental Manager, Vápenka Vitošov s.r.o.

Petr Ston – Vápenka Vitošov s.r.o.

Anita Bartakovics – Senior geologist, Dept. Geo-Services, Gas Storage CZ s.r.o.

Eliška Pecinová – Gas Storage CZ s.r.o.

Pavel Merta – Economic Director, UNIGEO a.s.

Tomáš Mazálek – Development Projects Manager, Heidelberg Materials CZ, a.s.

Václav Příbylík – Heidelberg Materials CZ

Minutes:

Welcome and introduction by Juraj Franců

Membership in the End-User Group (EUG) of the CO2-SPICER project results was offered to the invited Government and Industry representatives. The benefits include direct access to all deliverables, such as reports and data, resulting from the Work Package activities.

In the following discussion partners from industry emphasized the need of bringing balance between the ETS unit price growth, company economy and by the financial support of the government. Extensive discussions undergo at the governmental level in the European Union and the Czech Republic. Lime producers plan to invest in new combustion facilities but external European or national funding is inevitable to build Carbon Capture plant (up to 3 bil CZK).

Transportation is additional part of the complex task of CO₂ emissions reduction activities and needs to be solved at national and European level.

The CO₂ storage comes as the next task. Here more effort needs to be undertaken as the CO₂ production is of much higher order of magnitude than the calculated storage capacity of the planned pilot.

From the European CCS scenarios it follows, that carbon storage is just one player in the future development. Its role is, however, important along with CO₂ usage as raw material for other productions and mainly the energy savings.

The contributions by the invited members of the End User Group was greatly acknowledged by the CO2-SPICER team. Details regarding the EUG administration will be further negotiated by e-mails.

Notes taken by Juraj Franců

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil. grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

T A
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